

A MULTISCALE APPROACH OF CALCULATING INITIAL FAILURE AND RESIDUAL STRESSES IN CFRP

Bodo Fiedler¹, Thomas Hobbiebrunken², Claas de Jong¹, Masaki Hojo²

¹*PolymerComposites, Technical University Hamburg-Harburg, Nesspriel 5, 21129 Hamburg, Germany*

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8501, Japan*

SUMMARY: A combined experimental and numerical study has been carried out in order to study the mechanism of initial failure in transversely loaded CF/epoxy composites. A low temperature-curing matrix optimised for RTM technology was investigated. Three-point bending experiments on macroscopic composite specimen with special laminate lay-ups were carried out in a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The In-situ experiments allow observing the onset of microscopic composite failure under transverse loading and measurement of the global applied load at onset of failure. The experimental results show that interfacial failure was the dominating failure mechanism. The interfacial stresses at initiation of failure were determined successfully by a non-linear micro/macro FE-Analysis (FEA). The results were compared with experimental results and the results obtained by using CLT. The results show that the interfacial normal strength (INS) between fibre and matrix governs failure under bending load.

KEYWORDS: Initial failure, Fibre/matrix bond, Interface/interphase, Transverse cracking, Residual stress, Finite-element analysis, In-situ testing, CLT

INTRODUCTION

The state of the art criteria [1,2,3] to describe the failure of composite structures are based on homogenised properties of fibre and matrix and can not regard on the micro-mechanical level of fibre and matrix. On the micro-mechanical level many models exist to describe the fracture phenomena observed in composites. High performance composites are cured at higher temperatures, after curing and cooling the composite is subjected to residual stresses. The resulting tri-axial stress state has a strong effect on the mechanical performance of composites. It is revealed that the presence of residual stresses reduce the transverse strength to failure [4]. In former work [5], the authors showed that the local fibre volume fraction has an strong influence on the residual stress state and initial matrix failure. The failure behaviour of epoxy resins was studied and discussed in detail [6,7]. Prediction of residual stresses and induced matrix failure requires knowledge of the temperature dependent mechanical and thermal properties of the constituents and the shrinkage of the matrix during curing. The temperature dependent non-linear matrix behaviour is one of the most important among them, because matrix plasticity and relaxation during curing at high temperatures lowers the residual

stress. However, thermal residual stresses have strong influences on the failure of composites, especially under transverse loadings [8,9]. The microscopic stress state in a cross-ply laminate is much more complex than in a UD-laminate. As we pointed out in our former papers, the microscopic stress state in a UD-laminate is mainly affected by the properties of the constituents, the fibre volume fractions and the distribution of the fibres in the matrix [10]. On the macroscopic level a UD-laminate is stress free after cooling. When a cross-ply laminate is cooled down, residual stresses are caused on the microscopic as well as macroscopic level. The latter effects are the influence of different ply-properties, the thickness of the plies and the thermal and mechanical load resulting from the structure [11].

Figure 1: The different stress levels in composite materials.

The initial failure of the composite happens on the microscopic level, either by matrix cracking or fibre-matrix debonding. The interfacial properties are of major interest in field of composite materials. Several micromechanical test methods exist: fragmentation test [12], single fibre pull-out test [13,14], micro droplet shear test [15], micro-indentation test [16] and Broutman test [17] to determine the interfacial properties from model composites containing one or few fibres. The obtained results are limited in their transferability and universality and in case of a strong fibre/matrix interface most of the test are give misleading results [18]. Hence measuring the interfacial strength from 90° off-axis tests often show higher significance to interfacial properties [19]. Furthermore the determined interfacial strength is directly correlated to the macroscopic composite strength [20].

Transferring the results obtained on a micro-mechanical level to the level of composite structures is difficult. The present work regards on this problem. The finite element analysis is used to link the micro-mechanical approach with the homogenised description of composite structures. CFRP bending specimens with unidirectional 90° fibre orientation and cross ply laminates with varying numbers of 0° and 90° oriented layers were manufactured by V-RTM technique. The initial failure of the fibre/matrix interface and matrix cracking were investigated by in-situ 3-point bending test [25] and compared with calculations by CLT and FEA.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

As reinforcement, the unidirectional-carbon-fibre fabric, G1157 D1300 INJECTEX E01 2F, from HEXCEL Composites was used. The fabric consists of 96% carbon-fibre rowings (HTA 5131 400TEX 6K TO AERO, Toho Tenax) in warp direction and 4% fixing E-glass-fibre yarns in weft direction. The carbon fibres are PAN based high-tenacity fibres. For the matrix the low viscosity L135i epoxy resin with the amine hardener H137 (both M.G. Scheuffler Kunstharzprodukte GmbH, Bakelite, Germany) both optimised for RTM was used. Resin and hardener were mixed and cured according the suppliers standards [21]. Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) panels were manufactured by resin-transfer-moulding (RTM) containing 11 plies of the fabric. To prepare samples containing only UD-carbon fibres the portion of weft glass fibre rovings were removed in sections from the UD plain weave fabric before resin infusion. The final zebra crossing like textile consisted of areas containing only UD carbon fibres and a hybrid fabric consisting of glass and carbon fibres. Five different lay-ups were chosen $[90_{11}]$, $[90_4/0_3/90_4]$, $[90_3/0_5/90_3]$, $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ and $[90_1/0_9/90_1]$. The operating pressure in the vessel was $P=0.2$ MPa and the supporting vacuum in the trap was less than $P<0.005$ MPa. After injection, the resin was cured for 48 hours at 25°C and post cured at 80°C for 24 hours. The final composites had a fibre volume fraction of 60%.

Three point flexure specimens of the dimension $3\times 3\times 30$ mm³ (width, thickness, length) were cut from the manufactured laminate plates without glass fibres. The distance between the bearings was 20 mm. The ply lay-up and the orientation during testing are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the 3 point bending test and the different lamina tested; a) $[90_{11}]$; b) $[90_4/0_3/90_4]$; c) $[90_3/0_5/90_3]$, d) $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ and e) $[90_1/0_9/90_1]$.

For specimens with a high $90^\circ/0^\circ$ -layer ratio initial failure was difficult to observe, because ultimate failure occurred without any initial cracks. In specimens with a lower $90^\circ/0^\circ$ layer ratio it was easier to observe initial cracks, because of the higher bending stiffness due to the higher number of 0° -plys. Often the initial failure occurred close to the lower $90^\circ/0^\circ$ -boundary and not at the bottom surface where the maximum bending tensile stress is acting. The SEM images were taken at the 90° -layer region at the tensile side of the bending specimen close to the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ boundary. To observe the entire area where initial failure can be expected is time consuming. Due to this fact the load was applied very slowly and for specimens with low bending stiffness $[90_{11}]$ relaxation may be occurred and the results.

Figure 3 shows a typical failure of a $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ laminate; many interfacial cracks, which grow and connect to a macroscopic crack when the load is increased. It can be seen that many initial interfacial cracks are generated at the same time. Small matrix bridges are left between those interfacial cracks. Further loading causes crack opening and large plastic deformation

under shear mode in the bridged matrix parts. Finally those resin bridges fail and final failure occurred. Interfacial failure was identified to be the dominating failure mechanism.

Fig. 3: Crack growth in the 90°- bottom ply of the $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ laminate from initial failure at an applied load of 256 N; 417 N (a), 373 N (b), 432 N (c).

LAMINAE TRANSVERSE STRESS

The properties of fibre and matrix were taken from our former work [22]. The resulting elastic constants and thermal properties of the ply and laminates were calculated using a commercial software package Compositor [23], all data are summarized in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Elastic and thermal properties of the neat resin L135i, the HTA carbon fibre and the composite L135i/HTA ($V_f=60\%$).

Constant	L135i resin	HTA fibre	Composite ($V_f=0.6$)
Modulus in fibre direction E_1 [GPa]	3	238	144
Transverse modulus E_2 [GPa]		28	6.4
Shear modulus G_{12} [GPa]	1.1	50	2.7
Shear modulus G_{23} [GPa]		5	2.3
Poisson ratio ν_{12} [1]	0.35	0.23	0.28
Poisson ratio ν_{21} [1]			0.01
Poisson ratio ν_{23} [1]	0.35	0.5	0.4
CTE α_1 [$10^{-6}/K$]	50	-0.1	0.3
CTE α_2 [$10^{-6}/K$]	50	10	28

Due to the lamina anisotropy thermal residual ply stresses are generated. In Fig. 4a the stresses transverse to the fibre direction are given for the different lay-ups. For UD-laminates the these stresses are not existing per definition. In case of the bi-directional laminates the contribution of the number of plies with different orientation is only small and has its minimum value of 13.1 MPa for the $[90_4/0_3/90_4]$ Laminate and increases to 14.7 MPa for the $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$. Residual stresses caused no failure in all specimens.

However, initial failure was observed relatively early during mechanical loading in laminates with relatively thin 90°-plies ([90₁/0₉/90₁] and [90₂/0₇/90₂]). The observed initial failure does not directly lead to ultimate failure of the 90°-ply. In fact, failure occurs over a wide scatter of the maximum 90°-ply stress values. We observed initial failure at a macroscopic transverse bending stress of 58 MPa - 96 MPa, calculated by CLT and the force measured in the in-situ bending test. The corresponding transverse stress distributions for the different laminates below the load line are summarised in Fig. 4b. It can be seen that for more balanced laminates the transverse failure stress is about 2 times higher (83-96 MPa) than in the case of UD-laminate or only one 90°-ply at the bottom surface (58 MPa).

Fig. 4: a) Macroscopic residual ply stress distribution transverse to the fibre direction for the different laminates; b) Macroscopic transverse tensile stresses (including residual stresses) according to the corresponding bending load from Tab. 2; the black dot represents the results from transverse tensile tests [22].

The transverse stress of 36 ± 5 MPa measured by standard transverse tensile test is also drawn as black dot in Fig. 4b. The value is again much smaller than measured in the bending test caused by the much larger volume tested in the tensile test. However, the differences of the residual stress distributions are rather small and can not explain the observed differences in transverse ply strength.

CONNECTING MICRO AND MACRO LEVEL

Figure 5 introduces the proposed multi-scale approach. In the discrete area the matrix is allowed to yield and relax during cooling down from the curing temperature. The matrix mechanical behaviour is non-linear and depends on time, temperature and stress. The unit cell and the bending beam are made by two dimensional 4-node plane strain elements. Owing to symmetry only one half of the bending beam was modelled. The unit cell consists of matrix and fibres. We assume a periodic array of the fibres in the matrix. The homogeneous composites were assumed to be orthotropic. The homogenized elasticity tensor C_{ijkl} and the thermal properties were calculated from the average stress or displacement in the microscopic unit cell for an applied strain or temperature change, respectively.

However, a huge amount of computational costs are necessary in order to solve a non-linear micro-macro analysis. Takano et al. [24] proposed a simplified non-linear algorithm, which

separates the microscopic and macroscopic analysis. In a first step the homogenized properties are calculated and stored in a database. In the following step the homogeneous calculation is carried out using the properties stored in the database. We used a similar approach in the present work. The commercial finite element software Marc™ (version 2003) with the pre- and postprocessor Mentat™ to carry out the FE-Analysis (FEA). Stress and strain of the composite at the macroscopic and microscopic levels were analyzed by homogenization of the composite microstructure. The macroscopic strains and perturbations were written in a FORTRAN code and implemented into the calculation using a MARC specific subroutine [25].

Figure 5: Linking micro- and macro-level; schematic illustration of the homogenization process using FE-Analysis, (a) micro model and (b) macro model [25].

Residual stress

The residual radial stress component is oriented to the centre fibre of the hexagon unit cell; the distributions are shown in Fig. 6. For the UD- [90°] -laminate the well known symmetric stress pattern can be observed (Fig. 6a).

Fig. 6: Thermal residual radial stress distribution in the hexagonal unit cell for a) [90₁₁] -laminate and b) [90₂/0₇/90₂] -laminate.

The radial stress at the fibre matrix interface is always compressive along the circumference the maximum value is $\sigma_R = -0.9$ MPa. In the case of 0° -plies come into play the microscopic stress distribution becomes non symmetric (Fig. 6b). The maximum residual radial stress at the fibre-matrix interface was calculated to $\sigma_R = 17.4$ MPa and occurred in the $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ - laminate.

Bending stress

The macroscopic strain state was calculated by the macroscopic FEA from the measured load at the moment of failure initiation. This strain state was transferred to the microscopic analysis, as described above. We assumed that initial failure directly lead to final failure for specimens in which we could not observed initial failure. In this case the strain state at ultimate 90° -ply failure was used in the micromechanical calculation.

Figure 7 shows the radial stress pattern for the UD-laminate (a) and the $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ laminate (b), respectively. The stress pattern is for both laminates identical showing a 4-fold symmetric distribution owing to the periodic arrangement of the fibres. According to the measured failure load, the stress level of the local matrix stresses are much higher for the cross-ply laminates compared to the UD-laminate.

Fig. 7: Radial stress distribution in the matrix for the measured bending force P at failure; a) $[90]$ laminate and b) $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ laminate.

The maximum radial stress on the microscopic level occurs transverse to the fibre. The maximum value of $\sigma_R = 118$ MPa was calculated for the $[90_3/0_5/90_3]$ laminate at an applied failure load of $P = 156$ N. In case of the $[90_4/0_3/90_4]$ laminate a very similar maximum stress of $\sigma_R = 111$ MPa was calculated; the corresponding failure load was of $P = 84$ N. For the 3rd cross-ply laminate $[90_2/0_7/90_2]$ the failure occurred at an applied bending load of $P = 256$ N which yields to a maximum radial stress of $\sigma_R = 115$ MPa. The transverse ply strength is constant in case of the cross ply laminates. When the number of 0° -plies becomes smaller the microscopic transverse strength decreases to 77% of the maximum strength for the $[90_1/0_9/90_1]$ laminate and in case of the UD-laminate only 66% strength can be reached. The

resulting radial or normal to the interface (INS) for all investigated specimen are summarized in Tab. 2. It is remarkable that the radial stresses in the matrix are higher than the corresponding strength of the neat resin L135i $\sigma_r=80$ MPa [22]. The resin strengths can be explained by size effects on the strength of brittle materials, like epoxies [26]. Regarding the volume between the fibres in a composite, the specific volume (volume per unit length), which can contain flaws, is in the order of 10^{-5}mm^2 , whereas the specific volume of the smallest tested bulk specimens was in the order of 1mm^2 . Hence there is a lower possibility of the existence of large and critical flaws in the composite resin than in the bulk resin. Therefore the strength of the composite resin is expected to be larger than the one of the bulk material.

COMPARISON

When we compare the results obtained by the micro-macro FEA with the results getting by CLT we get similar results, but the values of stress are higher for the microscopic calculations. In case of the thermal residual stresses the CLT leads to stresses of 82% to 91% of the maximum radial stress calculated by FEA. When load is applied the maximum microscopic stresses in the interface vary from 1.2 times up to 1.6 times of the macroscopic transverse stresses in the 90° -ply. These transverse stress magnification is similar to values found in the literature (1.5 to 1.9) for similar materials [27]. When the stress magnification around the transversely oriented fibres will be considered in the CLT the results will be very similar to the results obtained by the FEA.

Table 2: Residual ($\Delta T=-55\text{K}$) and bending stresses calculated by CLT and FEA from the measured bending force P.

Lay-up	Max residual transverse stress (CLT) [MPa]	Max residual radial stress (FEA) [MPa]	Measured bending force P* [N]	Max lamina transverse stress (CLT) [MPa]	Max radial stress (FEA) [MPa]
[90 ₁₁]	0	-0.9	51	58	78
[90 ₄ 0 ₃ 90 ₄]	13.1	14.4	84	89	111
[90 ₃ 0 ₅ 90 ₃]	14.3	17.4	156	96	118
[90 ₂ 0 ₇ 90 ₂]	14.7	17.4	256	83	115
[90 ₁ 0 ₉ 90 ₁]	14.6	17.3	304	58	91

*is the applied force when failure was observed.

CONCLUSIONS

A combined experimental and numerical study is a useful tool to characterize the failure in CF/epoxies. In-situ observations provide important information about transverse failure initiation and crack propagation. The use of cross-ply laminates turned out to be useful, since the tensile stress in the 90° -ply is easily controlled. The onset of failure and the failure process is successfully observed. A non-linear finite element analysis provided quantitative values of the stresses acting in the interface at initiation of failure.

The ply transverse strength is higher in cross-ply laminates compared to UD laminates under transverse bending load.

FEA and CLT give qualitatively same results for the thermal residual stresses as well as for the transverse stresses caused by the bending load. When the microscopic stress magnification in the matrix is considered in the CLT the stress values will be very similar to the micromechanical results obtained by FEA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported in the frame of the collaborative program of the German Research Foundation (DFG) and the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS).

Grateful thanks to the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology for the International Doctoral Program in Engineering at Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University.

The authors acknowledge to the Center of Excellence COE for Research and Education on Complex Functional Mechanical Systems for their support.

REFERENCES

1. Hill, R., *The Mathematical Theory of Plasticity*, Oxford University Press, London 1950
2. Tsai, S.W., Wu, E.M., "A general theory of strength for anisotropic materials", *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1971, 5 pp. 58-80
3. Puck, A., Schnürmann, H., "Failure analysis of frp laminates by means of physically based phenomenological models", *Composites Science and Technology*, 58, 1998, pp. 1045-1067
4. Fiedler, B., Hojo, M., Ochiai, S., "The influence of thermal residual stresses on the transverse strength of CFRP using FEM", *Composites: Part A*, 33 2002, pp. 1323-1326
5. Fiedler, B., Hojo, M., Ochiai, S., Schulte, K., Ochi, M., "Finite-element modelling of initial matrix failure in CFRP under static transverse tensile load", *Composites Science and Technology*, 2001, 61, pp. 95-105
6. Fiedler, B., Hojo, M., Ochiai, S., Schulte, Ando, M., "Failure behaviour of an epoxy matrix under different kinds of static loading", *Composites Science and Technology*, 2001, 61, pp. 1615-1624
7. Fiedler, B., Hojo, M., Ochiai, S., "The parabolic failure criterion applied to epoxy resins", *Proceedings of International Conference on new Challenges in Mesomechanics*, Aalborg, Denmark, August 26-30, 2002 pp. 533-539
8. Asp, LE, Berglund, LA, Talreja, R., "Prediction of matrix-initiated transverse failure in polymer composites", *Compos Sci Technol*, 1996; 56, pp. 1089-1097
9. Blacketter, DM, Upadhyaya, D, King, TR., "Micromechanics prediction of the transverse tensile strength of carbon fiber/epoxy composites: The influence of the matrix and interface", *Polym Compos*, 1993; 14, pp. 437-446
10. Hobbiebrunken, T., Hojo, M., Fiedler, B., Tanaka, M., Ochiai, S., Schulte, K., "Thermomechanical analysis of micromechanical formation of residual stresses initial matrix failure in CFRP", *JSME International Journal Series A*, 2004, 47.

11. Manson, J.E., Seferis, J.C., "Process Simulated Laminate (PSL): A Methodology to Internal Stress Characterization in Advanced Composite Materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1992, 26,3, pp. 405 – 430
12. Zhou, X.-F., Wagner, H.D., Nutt, S.R., "Interfacial properties of polymer composites measured by push-out and fragmentation test", *Composites: Part A*, 32 (2001), pp. 1543-1551
13. Tanaka, K., Minoshima, K., Grela, W., Komai, K. "Characterization of the aramid/epoxy interfacial properties by means of pull-out test and influence of water absorption", *Compos Sci Technol*, 62, 2002, pp. 2169-2177
14. Ramanathan, T., Bismarck, A., Schulz, E., Subramanian, K. "Investigation of the influence of acidic and basic surface groups on carbon fibres on the interfacial shear strength in an epoxy matrix by means of single-fibre pull out test", *Compos Sci Technol*, 61, 2001, pp. 599-605
15. Hoecker, F., Karger-Kocsis, J. "Effects of the interface on the mechanical response of CF/EP microcomposites and macrocomposites", *Composites*, 25, 1994, pp. 729-738
16. Ho, H., Drzal, L.T., "Evaluation of interfacial mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites using the microindentation method", *Composites: Part A*, 27, 1996, pp. 961-971
17. Ageorges C., Friedrich K. and Ye L. "Experiments to relate carbon-fibre surface treatments to composite mechanical properties", *Compos Sci Technol*, 59 (1999), 2101-2113.
18. Hojo, M., Terashima, K., Igarashi, Y., Shida, M., Ochiai, S., Inoue, T., Sawada, Y., Suzuki, Y. "Interfacial fracture in model composites under static and fatigue loadings - Mechanism consideration based on experimental and analytical approaches -", *Materials Science Research International, Special Technical Publication -2*, 2001, pp. 189-196.
19. Piggott, M.R., "Why interface testing by single-fibre methods can be misleading", *Compos Sci Technol*, 57, 1997, pp. 965-974
20. Madhukar, M.S., Drzal, L.T. "Fiber-matrix adhesion and its effect on Composite mechanical properties: II. Longitudinal (0°) and transverse (90°) tensile and flexure behavior of graphite/epoxy composites", *J Composite Materials*, 25, 1991, pp. 958-991
21. MGS – Injection resin L135i/H137i product data sheet; <http://www.mgs-online.com/>.
22. Fiedler, B., Gagel, A., Hobbiebrunken, T., Hojo, M., Schulte, K., Ochiai, S., "Modelling of the transverse strength of fibre reinforced epoxy composite at low and high temperature", *Composite Interfaces, special issue from IIMM*, 2003, accepted
23. Fischer, O., *Compositor software for the design of composite materials*, Version 2.0, Institut für Kunststoffverarbeitung (IKV) Aachen, 2003
24. Takano, N., Ohnishi, Y., Zako, M., Nishiyabu, K., "Microstructure-based deepdrawing simulation of knitted fabric reinforced thermoplastics by homogenization theory", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 38, 2001, pp. 6333-6356
25. Hobbiebrunken, T., Hojo, M., Adachi, T., Jong, C.D., Fiedler, B., "Evaluation of Interfacial Strength in CF/Epoxy using FEM and in-situ Experiments", *Composites Part A*, 2005, accepted
26. Odom, E.M., Adams, D.F., "Specimen size effect during tensile testing of an unreinforced polymer", *J Mat Sci*, 27, 1992, pp. 1767-1771
27. Adams, DF, Roner, DR., "Transverse Normal Loading of a Unidirectional Composite", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1, 1967, pp. 152 - 164